

In tertiary mixtures, Mg/Cu/Mn/Ca/Ni was eluted by 80% acetone-3 M CA, Co by 60% acetone-3 M CA, and Zn/Cd was eluted finally by 20% acetone-0.5 M CA and 5% acetone-0.1 M CA, respectively.

Fig. 1 shows separations of Co^{2+} from Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Mg^{2+} and Ca^{2+} .

The comparison with our earlier results³ reveals that the distribution coefficients of Cd^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and Co^{2+} in CA are greater than those in acetic acid, while those of Ca^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Mn^{2+} are less in CA. These values suggest higher separation factor. The metal ions are thus carried with low volume of eluent and with less duration.

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Substituted Benzophenones as Possible Prodrug Forms of Benzodiazepine Anxiolytics

Y. D. KULKARNI, S. H. R. ABDI and V. L. SHARMA

Department of Chemistry, Lucknow University,
Lucknow-226 007
and

P. R. DUA and G. SHANKER

Pharmacology Division, Central Drug Research Institute,
Lucknow-226 007

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A prodrug form utilises a chemical moiety of proven biological activity (parent molecule) and seeks to deliver it to the site of action, while overcoming some inherent drawbacks, such as bitterness, odour, gastric upset, poor absorption and unsuitability for administration, etc. associated with the parent compound. A prodrug¹, upon introduction to the appropriate biological system, reverts to the parent molecule by virtue of enzymatic and/or chemical liabilities. Thus, peptidoaminobenzophenones² were prepared as prodrug forms of benzodiazepines with a view to obtain a stable water

soluble product, suitable for parenteral administration. These compounds furnished 1,4-benzodiazepines at the site of action by enzymatic cleavage of terminal amide linkage, followed by chemical cyclisation. Prompted by these observations, the authors became interested in the synthesis and biological testing of 2-[N'-substituted-glycylamino]-5-chlorobenzophenone and their higher homologues with

different types of terminal amide linkages to study the effect of enzymatic hydrolysis. Higher homologues were synthesised to observe the relative ease of the formation of seven-, eight- or nine-membered heterocyclic systems (Table 1).

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillary and are uncorrected. The reactions were followed by tlc. Ir spectra (KBr) of the samples were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 157 infracord and Perkin-Elmer 177 or 137 grating instruments. The pmr spectra were recorded on a Varian A 60D spectrometer (60 MHz) using CDCl_3 as solvent and TMS as internal standard.

2-Amino-5-chlorobenzophenone³ and 2-methylamino-5-chlorobenzophenone⁴ were prepared by known methods.

2-[N'-Substituted-glycylamino]-5-chlorobenzophenones and their homologues (1-8): To a solution of substituted amino acid (0.0015 mol) in dry dioxane (15 ml) was added thionyl chloride (0.003 mol) at 0° with stirring, and left standing overnight at room temperature. 2-Amino/methylamino-5-chlorobenzophenone (0.001 mol) and triethylamine (0.004 mol) were added to it and the mixture was heated on a water-bath for 1-3 h. The reaction mixture was poured over cold water (200 ml), and the crude product was filtered, dried and recrystallised from either ethanol or benzene-petroleum ether mixture in yields ranging 50-80%. The compounds were characterised by their m.p.s., elemental analyses and the presence ir spectral bands at 3300-3200 (amide NH), 2950 (methylene) and 1680 cm^{-1} (amide C=O).

2-[N'-Morpholinoacetylglycylamino]-5-chlorobenzophenone (9): A mixture of 2-[N'-chloroacetylglycylamino]-5-chlorobenzophenone (3; 0.001 mol), morpholine (0.0011 mol) and triethylamine (0.002 mol) in dry benzene (25 ml) was refluxed for 10 h. The separated triethylamine hydrochloride was filtered off, the filtrate concentrated under reduced pressure and the residue recrystallised from benzene-petroleum ether mixture in 60% yield. The

TABLE 1—2-[N'-SUBSTITUTED-GLYCYLAMINO]-5-CHLOROBENZOPHENONES AND THEIR HOMOLOGUES*

R₁ = CH₃ for 4-6 and H for others ; n = 2 for 7, 3 for 8 and 1 for others.

Compd. no.	R	M.p. °C	Molecular formula	ALD ₅₀ mg/kg i. p. (confidence limit)
1	Benzamido	83-85	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ ClN ₂ O ₂	>1000
2	Acetamido	120-21	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ ClN ₂ O ₂	>1000
3	Chloroacetamido	138-39	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂	>1000
4	Benzamido	90-91	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ ClN ₂ O ₂	>1000
5	Acetamido	190-91	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ ClN ₂ O ₂	681 (nil)
6	Chloroacetamido	155-56	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂	—
7	Benzamido	97-98	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ ClN ₂ O ₂	825 (562-1210)
8	Acetamido	69-70	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ ClN ₂ O ₂	—
9	Morpholinoacetamido	66-67	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ ClN ₂ O ₂	>1000
10**	Phthalimido	208-9	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ ClN ₂ O ₂	>1000
	Oxazepam	—	—	825 (562-1210)

*All compounds analysed for C, H and N were found satisfactory.

**²H nmr δ (CDCl₃) 8.50 (1H, m, NH), 7.90-7.30 (12H, m, ArH) and 4.50 (2H, s, COCH₃N).

compound was characterised by its m.p., elemental analyses and ir spectral bands at 3400-3300 (amide NH), 2900 (methylene), 1670 (amide C=O), 1650 (diphenyl C=O) and 1600 cm⁻¹ (C—C phenyl).

2-[2'-Phthalimidoacetamido]-5-chlorobenzophenone (10): Thionyl chloride (0.04 mol) was added to phthalimidoacetic acid (0.0015 mol) and the mixture was refluxed for 6 h. Excess of thionyl chloride was distilled off and the residue dissolved in chloroform (10 ml). To this solution was added 2-amino-5-chlorobenzophenone (0.001 mol) and refluxed for 3 h. The reaction mixture was concentrated under reduced pressure and the residue recrystallised from CHCl₃-petroleum ether mixture in 90-95% yield. The compound was characterised by its m.p., elemental analyses and ir spectral bands at 3250 (amide NH), 1780 (ArCONCOAr), 1710 (amide C=O), 1645 (ArCOAr) and 1600 cm⁻¹ (C—C phenyl).

Biological studies :

Albino mice and rats of either sex were used which weighed between 16-20 and 100-150 g, respectively. Aqueous suspension of the compounds were prepared in gum acasia. Oxazepam was used as standard in all the tests. The results have been summarised in Table 1.

Acute toxicity : The approximate lethal dose (ALD₅₀) was determined in groups of 4 mice each (24 h fasted) using the method of Horn⁶. An initial dose of 464 mg/kg of compounds was administered i.p. The doses of compounds were increased or reduced depending on the mortality observed with the initial dose. Mortality at 4 such doses was recorded and the Table was used to read the ALD₅₀ and confidence limit.

Gross behavioural effects : The method of Turner⁶ was used. Different doses of compounds including 1/5th ALD₅₀ were administered i.p. in groups of 4-5 mice each, which were then observed for 6 h and at 24 h for the signs of stimulation, depression, no observable effects and autonomic effects.

Anticonvulsant activity : The method of Swinyard *et al.*⁷ was followed.

(i) **Metrazole seizures threshold test :** Groups of 5 albino mice, pretreated with 1/5th ALD₅₀ of compounds i.p. were injected metrazole (80 mg/kg) subcutaneously after 1 h. The number of animals not exhibiting convulsions during 60 min after the injection of metrazole were expressed in terms of percentage protection. This test was also used as a model^{8,9} for anxiolytic activity as well.

(ii) **Supramaximal electroshock seizures test :** Groups of 5 albino mice were pretreated 1 h earlier with 1/5th ALD₅₀ of compound i.p. A current stimulus of 48 mA for 0.2 sec delivered through ear electrodes produced tonic extension of hind limbs in 100% of the mice in the control group. Abolition of this response by compounds was taken as criterion of their anticonvulsant activity.

Anxiolytic activity : The procedure of Poschel¹⁰ was used (a specific test for benzodiazepines). Albino rats in groups of 5 each were used. Saline treated controls were run concurrently. Food and water was available *ad libitum*. The sweetened milk suspension which is an unfamiliar food for rats was prepared afresh each day using 1 part milk powder and 2 parts water. The compound

suspension was administered orally 30 min prior to commencement of the experiment. The measured quantity of milk was offered in cavity blocks and milk intake was recorded after 60 min. Increased milk consumption (compared with control) in treated groups was taken as criterion of anxiolytic activity of the compounds.

Results and Discussion

The ALD_{50} of compounds 1-4, 9 and 10 was >1000 mg/kg i.p., for 8 and oxazepam it was 825 mg/kg i.p., and 5 had an ALD_{50} of 681 mg/kg i.p. At 1/5th ALD_{50} none of the compounds showed any effect on gross behaviour while oxazepam produced depressant effect. Compound 5 afforded 80%, 4, 7 and 10 showed 20%, and oxazepam produced 100% protection against metrazole induced seizures. 3 and oxazepam showed 20% and 80% protection, respectively against supra-maximal electroshock seizures. In addition 4 and oxazepam increased the milk consumption in non-fasted rats by 30% and 58%, respectively. Other compounds were devoid of this activity. Mean milk ingestion for control group was 5.16 ± 0.625 ml while for 4 and oxazepam it was 6.80 ± 0.415 and 8.2 ± 2.2 ml, respectively.

These results had suggested that enzymatic hydrolysis of terminal amide linkage was occurring and the acetamido linkage was found to be very facile among the amide linkages studied. Lesser activity among higher homologues (7 and 8) has led to the conclusion that formation of an 8- or 9-membered ring was not favoured. Thus, 2-[N'-substituted-glycylamino]-5-chlorobenzophenone with terminal acetamido linkage might be acting as the prodrug form of 1,4 benzodiazepines.

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Flavonoidic Constituents of *Rhus wallichii* Hook.f. (Anacardiaceae)

(Miss) FEHMEDA KHATOON, M. KHABIR
and
W. H. ANSARI*

Department of Chemistry, Aligarh Muslim University,
Aligarh-202 001

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SINCE the report of the isolation and characterisation of some novel biflavonoids¹ from *Rhus succedanea*, the genus *Rhus* has become the focus of attention for investigation in this field. In the present paper we report the isolation and identification of a biflavone together with flavonols and flavanol glycosides from the leaves of *Rhus wallichii* Hook.f. (Anacardiaceae). The co-occurrence of a biflavone with the flavonols and flavanol glycosides is the first example in *Rhus* genus.

Fresh leaves procured from Royal Botanical Garden, Godawari (Nepal), after thoroughly de-fattening by repeated extraction with light petroleum ether and benzene were extracted with acetone. The acetone extract was concentrated under reduced pressure and the residue left was treated successively with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°), benzene, chloroform and ethyl acetate. The ethyl acetate fraction was chromatographed over silica gel column and five flavonoidic compounds, A, B, C, D and E were obtained.

Compound A: The compound eluted by benzene-ethyl acetate (9 : 1) gave +ve Shinoda test, and was identified as kaempferol by comparison of its m.p. (276-78°), m.m.p., co-tlc and pmr data with the authentic sample.

Compound B: It was eluted by benzene-ethyl acetate (8 : 2), and was crystallised from acetone-methanol (1 : 1) as light yellow crystals, m.p. 316°, formed an acetate $C_{28}H_{30}O_{12}$, m.p. 197-98°, and was characterised as quercetin by comparison of m.p and pmr data of its acetate with the authentic sample.

Compound C: It was eluted by benzene-ethyl acetate (7 : 3), m.p. 254-56°, and was characterised as amentoflavone by comparison of its R_f value (0.16) (benzene-pyridine-formic acid, 36 : 9 : 5), characteristic fluorescence of its methyl ether (bright yellow) in uv light², and pmr data of its acetate with the authentic sample^{3, 4}; τ (CDCl₃) 1.99 (1H, d, J 3Hz, H-2'), 2.05 (1H, q, J 3 and 9Hz, H-6'), 2.52 (2H, d, J 9Hz, H-2''', 6'''), 2.56 (1H, d, J 9Hz, H-5'), 2.96 (2H, d, J 9Hz, H-3''', 5'''), 2.76 (1H, d, J 3Hz, H-8), 3.10 (1H, d, J 3Hz, H-6), 3.00 (1H, s, H-6''), 3.30, 3.35 (1H each, s, H-3,3''), 7.54, 7.60, 7.78, 7.75, 7.90, 7.98 (18H, 6 OAc).